

On Coagulation of Hydrosols by mixture of Electrolytes and Ionic Antagonism.

BY

JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE

AND

BHUPENDRA NATH GHOSH.

In a recent paper Freundlich and Scholz (*Kolloid. Chem. Beihefte*, 16, 267, 1922) have shown that the precipitating concentration of barium chloride is materially increased if the electrolyte contains in addition lithium chloride in concentrations which are not in themselves sufficient to cause coagulation. This effect has been observed with hydrosols of arseniousulphide and of sulphur prepared by Oden's method whereas for hydrosols of gold and of sulphur prepared by Weimarn's method the precipitating concentrations remain practically unaffected by such additions. It seems, as it were, the coagulating power of these cations decrease in the presence of a second cation. They found that this antagonism is very pronounced between univalent and divalent cations.

The greatest antagonism was observed between lithium and magnesium, further the effect was absent with gold sol which is not hydrated and they suggested that the effect is due to hydration of these ions and of the colloid.

Apart from considerations of hydration there are other possible factors which might account for the so-called antagonistic action of ions. It is usually assumed (though it rests on rather slender evidence cp. Mukherjee, Thesis of Doctorate of Science, University of London, 1921), that the concentrations of different electrolytes which

brings in the same rate of coagulation corresponds to a state of the colloid where the particles have the same density of electrical charge. If that view be correct the observed results might be ascribed to the following causes :—

(1) Difference in the adsorption of the anions and cations present. This is the point of view taken up by Weiser and his collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, *25*, 666, 1921), who consider that in the case of colloidal solutions of arsenious sulphide both the cations and anions are very largely adsorbed. Now in the mixture the anion concentration is higher than in the case of the electrolytes with a divalent cation, and there will be a greater adsorption of the anion. The negative charge on the particles is therefore greater. More cations must therefore be adsorbed to bring down the density of the electrical charge to the value which corresponds to the limiting concentrations. Weiser concludes that the higher coagulating concentration is an index of the greater amount of anion that has been adsorbed.

(2) Freundlich (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, *86*, 458, 1914) has pointed out that the adsorbability of one cation may be influenced by the other that is the presence of the univalent cation in comparatively higher concentrations might interfere with the adsorption of the bivalent cation and diminish its coagulating power.

It would seem that a study of the effect of various anions on coagulation by mixed electrolytes with simultaneous determination of the electrical charge will be most useful. The electrical data are essential for a proper understanding of the nature of the effect we are studying. It is to be regretted that there is very little useful data on this subject. In this laboratory a systematic study of the electrical charge is being carried out.

The present paper deals with the effect of various

anious on coagulation of arsenious sulphide hydrosol by mixed electrolytes.*

EXPERIMENTAL.

During the last few years, a number of papers has been published showing that arsenious sulphide sol has different chemical composition, depending on the methods of preparation.

In our work, we have always adhered to the same method of preparation. The following method has been adopted for determining equi-coagulating concentrations. Light from a single filament lamp is allowed to pass through a layer of definite thickness of the coagulating colloid and the time noted when the sharp outline of the filament disappears. The intensity of the light is kept constant by passing a definite current through the filament. Electrolytes are considered to have equi-coagulating concentrations when the time required for reaching the same stage of coalescence is the same in each case. For each pair of electrolytes used the mixtures as well as the individual electrolytes are exactly equi-coagulating. During an experiment the colloid is tested from time to time by determining the coagulating concentration of a particular electrolyte.

TABLE I.

% Concentration of Sodium Benzoate.	% Concentration of Barium Chloride.	Sum.	% Concentration of Calcium Bromide.	Sum.	% Concentration of Calcium Benzoate.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100	100	100
20	134	154	159	179	175	195
33	138	171	179	212	190	223
50	130	180	170	220	180	230
66	100	166	141	207	146	213

* Since this work was finished Weiser has published another paper on adsorption by precipitates (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 28, 237, 1924).

% Concentration of Sodium benzoate	% Concentration of Magnesium chloride.	Sum.	% Concentration of Barium benzoate.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100
20	182	202	150	170
33	203	236		
50	195	245	150	200
66	155	221	120	186

Coagulating concentration of Sodium benzoate mean—0.17 N* = 100
 " " " Barium chloride—0.0015 N = 100
 " " " Calcium bromide—0.0017 N = 100
 " " " Calcium benzoate—0.0018 N = 100
 " " " Magnesium chloride—0.002 N = 100
 " " " Barium benzoate—0.0014 N = 100

TABLE II.

% Concentration of Sodium benzoate.	% Concentration of Potassium chloride.	Sum.	% Concentration of Lithium chloride.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100
20	121	141	181	201
33	114	147	169	202
50	86	136	186	186
66	62	128	98	164

Coagulating concentration of sodium benzoate—0.16 N = 100
 " " " Potassium chloride—0.06 N = 100
 " " " Lithium chloride—0.08 N = 100

* The sum of cations given in the tables is the sum of the percentage concentration of each cation taking the coagulating concentration of each separately to be hundred.

The actual values for different pairs varied respectively from 0.166 N to 0.174 N. The difference in the coagulating concentrations of barium chloride and barium benzoate may be due to experimental errors. But nothing definite can be said until they are more carefully examined. The barium benzoate was prepared from baryta and benzoic acid,

Percentage concentration of sodium benzoate.	Percentage concentration of sodium chloride.	Sum.
0	100	100
20	141	161
33	125	158
50		
66	98	164

Coagulating concentration of sodium benzoate—0.18 N=100

„ „ „ sodium chloride—0.08 N=100

TABLE III.

% Concentration of sodium chloride.	% Concentration of barium chloride.	Sum.	% Concentration of calcium bromide.	Sum.	% Concentration of Magnesium chloride.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100	100	100
20	134	154	138	158	135	155
33					135	166
50	115	165	125	175	125	175
66	80	146	94	160	104	170

Coagulating concentration of sodium chloride (mean)—0.075 N*=100

„ „ „ Barium chloride—0.00155 N=100

„ „ „ Calcium bromide—0.0017 N=100

„ „ „ Magnesium chloride—0.002 N=100

TABLE IV.

% Concentration of sodium acetate.	% Concentration of Barium acetate	Sum	% Concentration of Barium chloride.	Sum.	% Concentration of Magnesium chloride.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100	100	100
20	164	164	156	176	210	230
33	176	209	158	191	238	266
50	170	220	136	188	239	279
66	130	196	125	191	175	241

* The actual values varied from 0.073 N to 0.078 N for different pairs.

Coagulating concentration of sodium acetate (mean)—0.19 N*—100
 " " " Barium chloride—0.0015 N=100
 " " " Barium acetate (approx.)—0.0014 N=100
 " " " Magnesium chloride—0.0019 N=100

Percentage concentration of sodium acetate.	Percentage concentration of calcium bromide.	Sum.	Percentage concentration of sodium chloride.	Sum.
0	100	100	100	100
20	191	211	178	198
38	208	241	155	188
50	204	254	121	171
66	174	240	85	151

Coagulating concentration of sodium acetate—0.18 N=100
 " " " Calcium bromide—0.0016 N=100
 " " " Sodium chloride—0.07 N=100

TABLE V.

Percentage concentration of Potassium Trichloracetate.	Percentage concentration of Barium Trichloracetate.	Sum.	Percentage concentration of Trichlor-acetic acid.	Percentage concentration of Barium Trichloracetate	Sum.
0	100	100	0	100	100
20	123	143	20	108	128
50	100	180	33	104	137
66	85	151	66	65	131

Coagulating concentration of Trichlor-acetic acid—0.04N=100
 " " " Barium Trichlor acetate—0.00156N=100
 " " " Potassium Trichlor-acetate—0.06N=100

Percentage concentration of Barium benzoate.	Percentage concentration Barium chloride	Sum.	Percentage concentration of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Percentage concentration of KCl.	Sum.
0	100	100	0	100	100
20	78	98	20	105	125
38	64	97	33	93	126
50	49	99	50	81	131
66	38	99	66	83	119

* The actual values varied from 0.187 N to 0.196 N for different pairs.

Coagulating concentration of Barium benzoate—0.0014	N=100
" " " Barium chloride—0.0015	N=100
" " " K ₂ F ₂ (ON) ₂ —0.2	N=100
" " " KCl	—0.07 N=100

Percentage coagulating concentration of LiCl.	Percentage coagulating concentration of Mg Cl ₂ *
0	100
25	200
50	220
75	233

DISCUSSION.

In their experiments neither Freundlich nor Weiser has used electrolytes other than chlorides. The question how far the adsorption of anions is responsible for the increase in the coagulating concentrations of the divalent cations remains open. They have used mixtures of electrolytes containing two cations. It has been shown by Weiser (J. Phys. Chem., 28, 1924, 241) that there is a displacement of adsorption of one cation by the other. It is therefore not clear whether the observed effect is to be attributed at least in part to the adsorption of anions or to some factor other than the adsorption of anions. If however the mixture of electrolyte contain only one cation and an increased concentration of the cation is necessary for the mixture we must conclude that anion adsorption is responsible for the effect. We have such an instance in the effect of sodium benzoate and sodium acetate on the coagulating concentration of sodium chloride. Displacement of adsorption of one cation by another is impossible since we have got only one cation.

It will be noted that sodiumacetate increases the coagulating concentration of sodium chloride almost to

* The data for the pair LiCl and MgCl₂ are taken from Freundlich's Kapillarchemie, p. 634 (1922), and added for comparison only.

the same extent as it does in the case of barium chloride. Similarly sodium benzoate has almost equal effects on sodium chloride and barium chloride. So we conclude that even in cases where the displacement of adsorption of one cation by another is not possible the effect of the anion is as pronounced as in the case where displacement of adsorption may occur in addition.

TABLE VI.

Percentage concentration of Lithium Chloride.	Percentage * concentration of Barium Chloride	Percentage concentration of Sodium Acetate	Percentage concentration of Barium Chloride	Percentage concentration of Sodium Chloride.
0	100	0	100	100
25	133	20	156	178
50	110	33	158	155
73	110	50	138	121
		66	125	85

It is therefore difficult to say whether the effects of sodium acetate on Barium chloride is due to the displacement of the adsorption of Ba^{++} ion or simply due to the adsorption of the anion. In a previous paper (Mukherjee and Chaudhuri, J. Chem. Soc., 1924, Vol. 125, p. 795) reasons have been given which indicate that acetate and benzoate ions are more strongly adsorbed than Cl^{-} ion. This observation is in agreement with the observed influence of sodiumacetate and sodium benzoate on $NaCl$. The anion adsorption in these cases is therefore clearly established.

Regarding the effect of $LiCl$ on $BaCl_2$, Weiser has attributed it to the displacement of Ba^{++} ion by Li^{+} ion as he has actually observed that the precipitate carries with it

* The result for the pair $LiCl$ and $BaCl_2$, are taken from Freundlich's *Kapillarchemie*, p. 634 (1922).

less Ba in the presence of LiCl than in its absence. It is however necessary to point out that this observation in itself does not justify Weiser's conclusion. Apart from the difficulties of interpreting analytical data on adsorption (cp. W. O. Ostwald *Koll-Z.* 30 (1919), 279), Weiser's observation only shows that a smaller number of barium ions are present in the "double layer." It does not follow that there is also a smaller number of barium ions fixed on the surface than in the other case. The distinction between the adsorbed ions which are free to move under an impressed electrical field and those which are not free to move has been overlooked. The relative ratio of the two cations per unit surface in the fixed layer of ions which really determine the diminution in the electrical charge is not necessarily identical with that in the freely moving second sheet of the Helmholtz double layer. Analytical data cannot evidently give an idea of the distribution in either layer. It gives the idea of the total effect due to both layers assuming that the adsorption of the solvent is negligible. Weiser's interpretation will be true if coagulation takes place when the particles are practically neutral as in that case there will be no freely moving ions and all the cations are fixed on the surface. There is no justification for such an assumption.

We would now point out that in all these cases the assumption of a small adsorption of an anion will be sufficient to explain the observed effects* without recourse being had either to considerations of hydration or to displacement of adsorption. If we consider the experiments of Ellis, Powis and Kruyt at low concentrations of the electrolyte we find that there is in most cases a slight rise in the negative charge when the electrolyte is KCl or LiCl. We see that in the case of a chloride with a cation

* Of course we cannot say that this is actually the case in the absence of relevant data on the electrical charge.

of low coagulating power the increase in the charge may be more pronounced (cp. the curves given by Freundlich Kapillariohemie,* page 354, 2nd edition). In that case there ought to be a gradation in the effects of electrolytes having common anion and cations of same valency but different coagulating power. The coagulating power of lithium is the weakest among the alkali metal ions and that of magnesium among the divalent cations Ba, Sr, Ca, Mg, etc. Both Freundlich and Weiser have observed that lithium and magnesium show the most pronounced effect. Our experiments also support this observation as will appear from the data given above. Where the anions are adsorbed to a marked extent the greater increase in the negative charge is reflected in a greater difference in the coagulating concentrations of different cations of the same valency. We notice that the influence of sodium benzoate is in the order

that is the reverse order of their precipitating power. If we now contrast the effect of mixing sodium chloride instead of sodium acetate or sodium benzoate we find that the individual variations between barium chloride, calcium bromide and magnesium chloride are scarcely perceptible. If the displacement of adsorption of these cations varied from one to another one would then have expected a greater difference between them. Magnesium in no way shows characteristic difference compared to barium or calcium. The anion adsorption in the case of

* If similarly in the case of arsenious sulphide there is an increase in the charge at low concentration of these chlorides then it is not necessary to assume either hydration or the displacement of adsorption. In collaboration with Mr. S. G. Chaudhuri measurements are being made on the variation in the rate of cataphoresis of Arsenious sulphide particles with the change in concentration of acids. So far HCl and H₂SO₄ have been studied. The variation in charge is very complicated and depends probably on whether we are dealing with an orange or yellow sol. on the concentration of H₂S and probably on the reaction between H ion and the stabilising ion adsorbed on the surface of the colloid.

the chlorides is less pronounced because we are dealing with a relatively less adsorbable anion and cations with fairly strong coagulating power. Our contention is that it is the initial rise in charge at low electrolyte concentration which is to a large extent responsible for all these effects. It does not matter whether the increase in charge is due to a strong adsorption of the anion or to a weak adsorption of the cation as in the case of sodium benzoate and lithium chloride respectively. Recognising that on the addition of a small quantity of an electrolyte (say up to 66% of its coagulating concentration) there is an increase in the charge, the protecting effect of such an increase will of course be more prominent if the coagulating cation has a weaker precipitating power. That is why we find so great an effect of lithium chloride on magnesium chloride or of sodium benzoate or sodium acetate on magnesium chloride. The effect of sodium acetate on calcium bromide is not in any way less pronounced than that of lithium chloride on magnesium chloride and the effect of sodium benzoate on lithium chloride is fairly comparable to that of lithium chloride on magnesium chloride.

Similarly potassium trichloracetate has a greater effect than the acid on the coagulating concentration of the barium salt in keeping with the lower coagulating power of the potassium ion compared to that of the hydrogen ion. The pair barium benzoate and barium chloride show a marked contrast to sodium benzoate and sodium chloride. The total barium ion concentration remains fairly constant. Whereas in the case of sodium acetate and sodium chloride the total sodium ion concentration becomes more than double the coagulating concentration of sodium ions when only sodium chloride is used. The difference is probably due to the low anion concentration of the barium salts and the greater coagulating power of

the barium ion. There ought to be from our point of view no increase of charge at low concentration of barium salts. The curves of Ellis and Powis show this peculiarity. Potassium ferrocyanide and potassium chloride on the other hand show a weaker effect than sodium acetate and sodium chloride. This is probably due to the greater coagulating power of potassium ion on the one hand and the weaker adsorption of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ ion on the other hand in spite of its higher valency as shewn in a previous paper.

We would again repeat that in order to clearly understand the nature of these effects the corresponding measurements of the charge is absolutely necessary and discussion on the displacement of adsorption might be profitably postponed till we have obtained the necessary data.

Lastly we would make a few observations on ionic antagonism as observed in nature. It is rather rash to draw conclusions from a few experiments on coagulation in the laboratory and to conclude from the similarity of effects that there is a similarity in the cause. At the same time we might suggest that at least one of the main causes which is responsible for ionic antagonism as observed by Lillie, Osterhout, Loeb and Clowes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 20, 1916) is the effect of the ions on the electrical charge of the dispersed system. The similarity in the effects is probably to be attributed to this common factor. Clowes states "whatever the ultimate theoretical interpretation may be the close correspondence between data accumulated in such widely diversified fields affords substantial evidence of the existence of some heretofore unappreciated fundamental physical principle" and this fundamental physical factor might be the electrical charge.

[*Received, Nov. 10, 1924.*]
